

ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION OF FRP STRENGTHENED CONCRETE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: Conventional rehabilitating and strengthening techniques provide a promising strengthening solution in structural concrete applications. However, the weight penalty, and subsequent corrosion of the steel material may eventually increase the overall maintenance cost on the long run. Accordingly, this drives the development and application of new materials and technologies, which extend the service life of many structures. One class of materials that is meeting these challenges is fiber reinforced composite materials (FRC); their use is becoming increasingly important for extending the service life of civil infrastructures. However, some issues regarding the performance of these materials under severe environmental conditions need further investigations. In this work, reinforced concrete beams strengthened with three types of composites were exposed to different environmental conditions, then their performance was compared to that of virgin specimens. Findings from experimental work will be used to derive and validate analytical models for the long term performance of these structures using the finite element method.

KEYWORDS: Concrete structures, strengthening, durability, degradation, long term performance, FEM.

INTRODUCTION

Durability and long term performance of fiber reinforced composite are important research issues, especially for materials intended for use in infrastructure and particularly in this region known for severe environmental conditions. In a recent study [1], surveys of structures in the Arabian Gulf region have shown an alarming degree of deterioration within 10 to 15 years of construction. In these surveys, 74% of the surface area observed in 42 concrete structures showed at least some severe deterioration. When reviewing some of the published work, it appears that most of the research performed was addressing mainly the strengthening issues [2,3], i.e, short term performance. While the durability and long term performance of the materials used is not well covered especially when dealing with hot climate. Actual data on durability is sparse, not well documented and/or not accessible to the civil engineer. In addition, there is a wealth of contradictory data published in a variety of venues that confuses the practicing engineer [4]. Consequently monitoring the durability of these materials is crucial towards their successful use as strengthening and repair materials.

Although a number of reviews have been published recently related to durability and test methods [5-7], the focus of each has been to summarize the state of knowledge in general without emphasizing or attempting to prioritize critical areas in which needs are the greatest for the collection, assimilation and dissemination of data. According to Karbhari et al [4] seven separate environmental conditions, moisture/solution, alkali, thermal (including temperature cycling and freeze thaw), creep and relaxation, fatigue, ultraviolet and fire are identified as being of primary importance vis-à-vis durability of FRP composites in infrastructure applications.

Besides durability, there still remain technological challenges prior to full acceptance of composite materials as repair and strengthening materials. These challenges include the development of reliable test methods, less expensive, yet sophisticated and specialized materials, viable and robust life prediction tools, as well as consideration of the environmental and mechanical response of these materials. Other significant hurdles include the absence of comprehensive data characterizing the long term durability of glass fiber reinforced polymeric composites with the absence of adequate established standards for repair, design and maintenance [8].

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Materials under investigation were subjected to accelerated environmental testing. Here, both the composite laminate and the strengthened concrete elements were subjected to testing. For concrete elements, since it was not possible to test the entire beam, it was decided to cast concrete “biscuits” having a square cross-section (25 mm x 25 mm) and a length of 150 mm. Then these biscuits were strengthened using the same procedure used previously for strengthening the plain concrete beams.

For the composite laminates, two types of experiments were considered. First, specimens were conditioned in an environmental chamber where specific conditions were prevailing. The chamber was constructed of corrosion-resistant materials enclosing eight fluorescent UV lamps, a heated water pan, and a rack for holding the test specimens. The conditions simulate the deterioration caused by sunlight and water as rain or dew according to the ASTM standard G-53. Specimens were alternatively exposed to ultraviolet light alone and to condensation alone in a repetitive cycle. The UV source was an array of fluorescent lamps, with lamps emission concentrated in the UV range. For condensation, the latter was produced by exposing the test surface to a heated, saturated mixture of air and water vapor, while the reverse side of the test specimen was exposed to the cooling influence of ambient room air. The specimens were under this environment for a total of 2000 hours, thus simulating exposure for more than 10 years at normal conditions.

Additional specimens were put in an oven where a fully saturated environment prevails. This environment was made possible by a continuous supply of distilled water, which is heated in order to bring the relative humidity to 95%. The oven was also continuously illuminated by ten UV lamps in order to provide a continuous UV radiation. Knowing the power of the lamps and the exposed area, it was possible to compute the intensity of the radiation which was close to 250 w/m². The test was performed for a period of six months and a weekly recording of the weight was taken.

The strengthened structural elements were subjected to two different types of testing as following: Exposure to high temperature and dry environment (oven) and exposure to high temperature and saturated environment (saturation bath).

For the high and dry environment, then elements were put in an oven, where an average temperature of 50°C was kept in order to assess the effect of high temperature condition on the strengthened elements. The testing duration was 6 months. Finally, reinforced concrete

elements were exposed to a fully saturated environment using a saturation bath device. This device contains hot water, having an average temperature close to 50°C. The concrete elements will be exposed to the vapor arising from the hot water. The testing duration will also be the same as the previous ones.

RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The composite specimens were subject to mechanical testing using three point bending test according to ASTM standard D790. Test results for the average flexural modulus for both conditioned (environmental chamber and oven) and virgin specimens are shown in Fig.1 and Fig. 2. It is worth mentioning that the obtained results were the average of five readings.

Fig. 1: Effect of long term conditioning on the flexural modulus.

Fig. 2: Effect of moisture and UV radiation on flexural modulus.

According to the results, long term testing simulating both exposure to wet and that to dry environments combined with UV radiation, results in a decrease of the flexural modulus of the composite laminate. This reduction in the mechanical properties was common to all types

of fibers. For instance, carbon composites saw its modulus decreasing from an average of 17 GPa to 14.8 GPa. Initial visual observation suggests that resin properties and the fiber/matrix interface are responsible for this degradation, but exhaustive results will be presented in the SEM section. The same trend was also observed with samples subjected to fully hot and saturated environment. The flexural modulus for all types of materials decreased except for glass/aramid specimens where the modulus after exposure show a small increase, which can be considered as being within the experimental permissible error.

Composite samples were also immersed in water for a period up to a sixth month. A bi-weekly recording of their weight was performed. According to the results shown in Fig. 3, a common behavior was observed for the three different materials. Actually it is possible to identify three different regions for the moisture performance of these samples. A first region characterized by a very low water intake, then a second region where a high water intake is recorder and finally a constant region where water intake reaches saturation.

Fig. 3: Weight gain following complete water immersion.

Longer immersion times resulted in lower flexural modulus for composite specimens as shown in Fig. 4. The lowest reduction was recorded for glass/aramid specimens. Fiber impregnation and the quality of the fiber matrix interface are the determining factors for the performance of these materials.

Fig. 4: Effect of water immersion on the flexural strength.

Concrete biscuits reinforced with different types of fibers and being exposed to hot and dry environment were also tested using a three point bending test. Here, only the maximum fracture load was recorded. Both normal and high strength concrete biscuits were used. Again conditioning for a longer time will affect the performance of these materials as shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 except for glass/aramid specimens where conditioned specimens showed higher fracture loads.

Fig. 5: Fracture loads for virgin and conditioned specimens (high strength concrete).

Fig. 6: Fracture loads for virgin and conditioned specimens (normal strength concrete).

SEM ANALYSIS

Specimens that were subject to environmental conditioning were tested under three point flexural bending test and the fractured surfaces were analyzed using the scanning electron microscope. Fractured surfaces of virgin samples were also analyzed for benchmarking.

Glass/aramid specimens

The analysis is concerned with virgin specimen, the aramid fibers are in the weft direction. According to the scanning electron micrographs, the fibers surface was clean and no resin debris were identified on the surface, thus suggesting that the failure was resulting mainly from matrix debonding at the fiber-matrix interface as shown in Fig. 7. Also one can see, some loosening occurring at the origin of the fiber, which could be attributed to a poor compatibility between the fiber and the matrix being used.

Fig. 7: Enhanced magnification showing clean fibers surface and some loosening at the fiber origin.

According to these observations (see Fig. 8), it is important to develop better coupling and surface treatment methods in order to enhance the adhesion between the fiber and the matrix. There was no evidence of poor wetting or the occurrence of voids in the specimen analyzed, which may contribute in the deterioration of the interface between the matrix and the fiber. Similar specimen surfaces that were subject to environmental then flexural testing were also analyzed using the scanning electron microscope. Failure was also resulting from a matrix-fiber debonding at the fiber-matrix interface. It is clear that there was a large gap surrounding the fiber; it looks like some yielding occurs to the matrix. It seems that the testing temperature was close to the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the resin.

Fig.8: Enhanced magnification showing large gap surrounding the fibers.

Carbon specimens

For the virgin specimens, failure occurs mostly through matrix cracking and delamination as shown in the scanning electron micrograph depicted in Fig. 9. Fibers and matrix are exhibiting a strong bond.

Fig. 9: Enhanced magnification showing matrix cracking and good adhesion between the fibers and the matrix.

For the specimens subjected to environmental testing, the failure was resulting from a matrix fiber debonding rather than matrix cracking as it was observed for the virgin specimens. It looks like the high temperature that was prevailing during conditioning and its long duration causes the matrix to yield (see Fig.10).

Fig. 10: Enhanced magnification showing large gaps surrounding the fibers at their origin.

FEM ANALYSIS

Besides experimental testing, work was undertaken in order to derive analytical models of the long term performance of strengthened concrete structures using the finite element method. As a first step, it was necessary to build and validate a model representing the concrete beam. The given reinforced concrete beam specimen loaded under 4-point bending, was analyzed numerically using finite element code ABAQUS. The results of the specimen strengthened with FRP are compared with the virgin reinforced concrete beam.

The actual experimental setup involves cylindrical roller supports at the bottom and load transfer from hydraulic press to the upper surface of the beam specimen using similar cylindrical rollers. The contact area between these cylindrical rollers and the beam specimen is approximated as 7.5 cm^2 for the specimen of 15 cm thickness. The loading is simplified as uniformly distributed pressure applied on this area. Quarter symmetry is used to model the specimen in ABAQUS. Planes of symmetry, loading area and the support are shown in Fig. 12. Concrete beam is reinforced by a steel frame embedded in the beam to provide strength in bending. The frame consists of four straight steel bars running parallel to the length of the beam. Since model is quarter symmetric, only two of these rods (having half of the total beam length) need to be modeled, as shown in Fig. 12. This figure also shows a thin layer of FRP at the bottom of the beam.

Smearred Cracking Concrete model available in ABAQUS/Standard is used to model the non-linear behavior of the reinforced concrete beam specimen. This smearred cracking model doesn't track individual "macro" cracks but the presence of cracks are entered into the finite element calculations by the way in which cracks affect the local stress and material stiffness, in the region where cracks are present. This model allows for a diminished shear retention option; as the shear cracks start appearing in the concrete beam specimen, its shear stiffness is diminished. This effect is modeled using shear retention option. This model also allows for post-failure "Tension stiffening" due to steel-reinforcement bars. Using this parameter, effects

of reinforcement interaction with concrete and strain softening behavior for the cracked concrete is included in the finite element (FE) model. The non-linear material properties used for simulating the given concrete beam, were determined using lab tests, published formulae and values.

To predict the non-linear collapse behavior of the concrete beam, modified Riks method available in ABAQUS, was used. In the Riks method, both loads as well as displacements are solved simultaneously, according to the beam deformation response. The load vs. displacement curve is shown in Fig.13 where the load is incremented automatically using Riks method, for the beam with above mentioned material data. The load in this curve is the total vertical load on the 2-points in 4-point bending, and the displacement is of the node at the bottom in the center of the beam where the displacement is expected to be maximum, at any given load. The response of the plain reinforced beam is compared with the response of the FRP strengthened reinforced beam.

Figure 12: Von-Mises Stress contours of FRP strengthened concrete beam showing Planes of symmetry, loading area and the support

Figure 13: Load vs. displacement curve for virgin normal strength concrete beam

As shown in Fig. 13, the beam strengthened with FRP has shown much higher strength and load carrying capacity than the plain reinforced concrete beam.

CONCLUSION

According to the experimental results performed either on actual concrete beams or on a lab scale, composite materials offer a very interesting alternative as a repair and strengthening materials. For the durability of the repaired structures, initial results suggest that exposure for longer time under the severe climatic conditions prevailing here may affect the performance of the materials. Especially if one know that these materials were initially developed for countries with different climatic conditions.

Scanning electron microscopy analysis suggests that poor compatibility between the fiber and the matrix is responsible for the drop in the mechanical properties of these composites. Also, resin properties were also affected by longer conditioning times. Accordingly it is important to address these issues in order to enhance the performance of these materials. For instance special resin formulations exhibiting higher glass transition temperature should be formulated. Also better surface treatment methods for the fibers should be developed in order to enhance the adhesion between the fibers and the matrix. It is also suggested that the current work on modeling these complex behaviors using the finite element method will help developing materials models that can be used to predict the long term performance of these materials, especially in these region and thus avoiding running very expensive experimental program to monitor their performance.

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